

ISic0429

Epitaph for Dominicus Macedon

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Constantin Pietschmann,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates**

37.0767995, 15.2848558

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: Not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. memoria Dominici Mace donis lege et recedere

3. [a]mici nolite tristere quia

4. [o]mnes morituri sumus

Apparatus

Text of CIL 10, 7149

Translation (en)

To the memory of Dominicus Macedon. Read and withdraw. Friends, do not
grieve because we are all
mortal.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491657

EDCS 21900491

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7149 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

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